

A Markov process model of the evolution of ecological networks

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Introduction

As a result of complicated interplays between many ecological and evolutionary processes, ecological networks exhibit well-defined structures.

We here model the temporal evolution of an ecological network in order to investigate how past evolutionary history affects the current network architecture.

Method

Assumption:

Species inherit not only the genetics of their ancestors, but also their interaction patterns: this is true particularly when interactions are closely linked to morphology and thus to genetics.

Model:

The evolution of an interaction between each pair of current or ancestral species is modelled as a discrete state continuous time Markov process, drawing on the Felsenstein's theory [1] of phylogenetic modeling.

The process describes the probability of changing between two possible states: the absence (S_0) and the presence (S_1) of an interaction, over time ($t \geq 0$). It can be completely defined by its instantaneous rate matrix Q :

$$Q = \begin{matrix} & S_0 & S_1 \\ \begin{matrix} S_0 \\ S_1 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} -\mu\pi_1 & \mu\pi_1 \\ \mu\pi_0 & -\mu\pi_0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

- μ is the interaction gain-loss rate parameter
- π_0 and π_1 are the probability of finding the process in state S_0 and S_1 respectively.

Parameter estimates:

π_0 and π_1 has been estimated as the observed empirical frequency of S_0 and S_1 respectively.

We inferred μ using a maximum likelihood approach.

Model testing

Using 53 empirically observed communities, compiled by Rezende et al. [2], composed of pollination and frugivory networks, we explored whether:

- Known networks are better explained by real phylogenies than by randomly generated phylogenies.
- Networks simulated under our model provide a better fit to the observed node-degree distribution than do other contending models.
- The nestedness properties predicted by our model are consistent with empirically observed values.

Results

- For 85% of the networks, we were able to reject the hypothesis that the network is independent of the phylogeny.
- It confirms that the structure of the current networks is partially influenced by the past evolutionary history of the species.

- The node degree distributions of 34% of the networks were best fit by our model and 36% by a truncated power law.
- Our model outperforms specialised parametric models on a third of the networks.

- Our model is rejected for 24 networks (45%), producing nestedness predictions that cannot not be rejected for the remaining 55% of them.

- The null model is rejected for 81% of the networks: the majority of the empirical networks were significantly nested.

Conclusion

- Our model provides an overall fit of multiple network structures while other models mainly focus on testing the influence of phylogenetic history in shaping specific network architecture.
- Knowledge of the phylogenies of the interacting species is sufficient to obtain simulated networks with realistic properties in many cases.

- When ecological change occurs rapidly compared to evolutionary change, ecological characteristics would not be conserved at the evolutionary time scale. In such cases our model do not fit well.

References

[1] Felsenstein, J. 2004. Inferring Phylogenies. Sinauer Associates, Sunderland, Mass.
 [2] Rezende, E. L. et al. 2007a. Effects of phenotypic complementarity and phylogeny on the nested structure of mutualistic networks – *Oikos* 116: 1919–1929.